

NUMERICAL STUDY OF PILE-SOIL INTERACTION IN GROUPS UNDER OC AND NC CONDITION

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ABSTRACT: Piles have been used as foundations for a very long time. Their use is often combined in groups to support higher loads. This paper presents a numerical study using finite element method to study the behavior of pile in groups, in particular: the load transfer. Pile foundation of a tower resting on sand lenses is modeled using finite element-based program, MIDAS GTS NX. Underneath the sand lenses, a compressible clay layer ($N_{SPT\ avg} = 10$ blows/ft.) is treated both as OC Clay and NC Clay to study their effects to the load transfer of a pile in group. The results show that the stiffness of the soil due to the degree of consolidation may shift the load distribution of the soils.

Keywords: pile-soil interaction, behavior of pile in group, bearing capacity ratio

INTRODUCTION

Piles have been used as foundations for a very long time. Their use is often combined in groups, especially when subjected to heavy load of high-rise buildings. In practical cases, which the soil profile is layered and compressible strata present below the piles, the settlement caused by these strata must be considered in the calculation of pile group settlement.

When situated on such cases, there is an issue on the initial state of stress of the compressible soil. Hence there is argument on whether the soil is Normally Consolidated (NC) or Over Consolidated (OC). For this reason, a numerical study is to be conducted to ascertain the state of stress and their effects to the behavior of pile in group. This study focuses on the load transfer behavior on pile in group under OC and NC Condition.

SOIL DATA, PILE CONFIGURATIONS, AND STRUCTURAL LOAD

Soil stratification consists of mainly clay soils, as shown in Figure 1. The surface layer (very soft clay) is treated as NC Clay and the clay layer at depth of 30 – 40 m is treated as OC Clay, with OCR of 2.

The compressible layer is located under the sand lenses at depth of 25 – 30 m. This layer will be treated both Normally Consolidated Clays and Over Consolidated Clays to study the effects to the behavior of piles.

For pile data, the dimension of piles is square of 45 x 45 cm², with embedment depth of 20 m. Pile configurations and location of the structural load is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Soil Stratification and Pile Data

For simplification in the analysis, all soil parameters are the same except the OCR and K_0 value of the compressible layer. Table 1 shows the soil parameters used in the analysis.

Table 1. Soil Models and Parameters

Layer	Model Type	Depth (m)	γ [kN/m ³]	ν	k_x [cm/s]	k_y [cm/s]	k_z [cm/s]	E_u [kN/m ²]	c_u, c' [kN/m ²]	ϕ_u, ϕ' [°]	OCR	λ	κ	K_0
(1) Very Soft Clay (N = 1)	Mohr-Coulomb	0-13	15	0.45	10^7	10^7	10^7	2000	5	0	-	-	-	-
(2) Stiff Clayey SILT (N = 10)	Mohr-Coulomb	13-20	15	0.3	10^6	10^6	10^6	18600	46.5	0	-	-	-	-
(3) Very Dense Silty SAND (N = 50)	Mohr-Coulomb	20-25	17	0.25	10^5	10^5	10^5	93000	0	40	-	-	-	4
(4) Stiff Silty CLAY (N = 10)	Soft Soil	25-30	17	0.3	10^8	10^8	10^8	-	-	-	2/1	0.1	0.0217	0.8 / 0.577
(5) Stiff Silty CLAY (N = 15)	Soft Soil	30-40	17	0.3	10^8	10^8	10^8	-	-	-	2	0.072	0.012	0.8
(6) Very Stiff Silty CLAY (N = 25)	Mohr-Coulomb	40-60	17	0.3	10^8	10^8	10^8	35000	116	0	-	-	-	-
(7) Dense SAND (N = 30)	Mohr-Coulomb	60-64	17	0.3	10^5	10^5	10^5	45000	0	35	-	-	-	-
(8) Very Stiff Silty CLAY (N = 25)	Mohr-Coulomb	64-80	17	0.3	10^8	10^8	10^8	35000	116	0	-	-	-	-

Figure 2. Pile Configurations (a), and Location of Structural Load (Point Load) (b)

PILE BEARING CAPACITY RATIO

In this study, new term of "pile bearing capacity ratio" will be introduced. The definition of pile bearing capacity ratio is the ratio of load on pile top to pile ultimate bearing capacity. The equation is as follows:

$$PBC = \frac{Q_m}{Q_{ult}}$$

where: Q_m = Load on Pile Top

Q_{ult} = Ultimate Bearing Capacity of Pile

NUMERICAL MODELING AND ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

In this study, settlement of pile group is numerically modeled using finite element-based program, MIDAS GTS NX. Soil layers and raft modeled with 3D solid elements, while piles modeled with beam elements. The interface of pile-soil and interface of pile-raft is also modeled. The whole model of the problem is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Soil Layer and Pile-Raft Model

Analysis of the problem conducted with stage construction. The stage are as follows:

1. Self-weight analysis for calculating the initial stress condition of the soil only, where the K_0 value of compressible layer is inputted.
2. Installing the piles
3. Excavate to elevation of -2.30 m (cut of level of -0.5 m + raft thickness of 1.6 m)
4. Pile cap construction
5. Apply structural load, where the load be applied gradually in 180 days.
6. Consolidation stage, where the consolidation time of 50 years.

RESULTS

Settlement Contour

Figure 4 shows the settlement contour both under OC and Condition. The contour gives relatively the same pattern, with maximum settlement occurs in the center of tower.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Settlement Contour under OC Condition (a), and NC Condition (b)

From the result, it shows that the difference of maximum settlement from both condition is quite significant. The differential settlement is also investigated with cross section 1-1 and cross section 2-2 in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Cross Section of Settlement under OC and NC Condition

The cross-section results show that the differential settlement become an issue if the compressible layer treated as NC Clay. Settlement at the center of tower, which is the concentration area of the structural load, caused a devastating differential settlement especially at Tower C (cross section 1-1). The settlement under NC condition can reach as twice as the settlement under OC condition.

Load Transfer Behavior of Pile in Group

To investigate the load transfer behavior, a large pile group and an investigated pile is chosen in the load concentration zone (center of tower). Contour of load at pile top under OC and NC condition were plotted in Figure 6.

From the contour, it shows that the contour relatively gives the same pattern. However, the load on pile top at the investigated pile gives different value. In order to investigate the load transfer behavior of the investigated pile, load transfer under OC & NC condition were plotted in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Contour of Load at Pile Top Under OC Condition (a), and NC Condition (b)

Figure 7. Load Transfer Profile at Investigated Pile Under Both OC and NC Condition

From the figure, the load at pile top under OC condition is bigger than under NC Condition (at investigated pile). Hence pile bearing capacity ratio under OC condition is also bigger than under NC condition. However, if we take a closer look at the contour, at the other side of investigated pile, the load at pile top gives relatively the same value. This is may be caused by the load concentrating in the area.

DISCUSSION

In most cases, the use of parameter from laboratory test is commonly conservative. Due to disturbance, the laboratory test results trend to be conservative or even over conservative and neglect the reality. In this particular case the result gives high settlement and consequently differential settlement. To obtain better results, insitu testing were conducted consisting of new SPT values and Pressuremeter Test. As predicted the clay is stiff and pre-consolidation pressure is higher. The recalculated settlement is much less.

SUMMARY AND LESSON LEARNED

In practical design of pile foundation, compressible layer beneath the foundation may present, which can lead the practical engineers into unfavorable condition. Their initial state of stress must be specified appropriately, as they can cause devastating differential settlement to the building. From this study, it can be concluded that the value of settlement under NC condition can be as twice as the settlement value under OC condition.

The load transfer behavior of pile in group is also consistent with the settlement result. A situation when the compressible layer is OC, which the soil is stiffer, the load at pile top is high. It means that the structural load is absorbed at the pile top, so the structural load that distributed to pile tip is low.

Another vice-versa situation, when the compressible layer is NC, which the soil is softer, the load at pile top is lower. It means that the structural load that distributed into pile tip is higher and caused the underlying layer to compress.

REFERENCES

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